

Applying Data Visualization Techniques for Online Tailoring Sales Analysis Using WEKA

Joe Tom Thomas
PG Scholar

Department of Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam Kerala, India
joetomthomas85@gmail.com

Dr. Manju K Mathai
Professor

Department of Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam Kerala, India
manjukmathai@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: Online tailoring management is a website which provides both stich and readymade dresses like salwar kameez, Kurtis etc. It is important for a business to analyze its achievements. This paper focuses on identifying most average and less sold products among the different products available in the business using Weka. The above process will help business in the future to select which product they should produce more, which product less, price management etc. This paper compares the output of various machine learning techniques like k -Nearest Neighbors (KNN), J48, OneR and Random Forest on the sales database of on-line tailoring web page. The different attributes present in the database are Product type, Product price, Date of Order and Total Price.

Keywords: Machine Learning, OneR, k-Nearest Neighbors, J48, Random Forest, Weka, Accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a type of statistics evaluation that will automate the introduction of analytical models for analysis. It's an area of artificial intelligence primarily based on the promise that computers can analyze from data, recognize patterns, and make decisions with minimum human intervention. This study objectives to find best algorithm to categorize the sales dataset based on different features using the distinct strategies of machine learning (ML).

By analyzing current behavior of buyers in India experts say the trend of online shopping is increasing gradually [1], so there will be an urge for customers to buy most of their products online to reduce time wastage and other expenses. In this online tailoring management system it tries to bring down the

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traditional way of going to shops for getting the materials stitched. This analysis is done to find which type of products is more preferred by the customer and is there any price constraints affecting the sales of other type of products. Analysis will help the online stitching providers to find which type of product should they stock more and find the forecast of each product and the business itself.

II. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this analysis is to classify the online tailoring sales using the attributes extracted from sales database. We are using this dataset to train a dataset, determine the best algorithm and its accuracy, and build a machine learning model for testing. The influence of consumer decision-making styles on online apparel consumption by college students". Apparel purchases now constitute one of the fastest-growing segments of e-commerce [2]. Thus it needs a strong analysis and train dataset to understand the customers characteristics associated with buying different products online.

III. METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to classify online tailoring sales dataset into two categories product type which is sold more and the product type which is least sold. This section classify the products based on the attributes. The methodology involves three main phases collecting dataset, pre-processing and classification of products.

A. WEKA

WEKA is a data mining tool developed by the University of Waikato in New Zealand that implements data mining algorithms. WEKA is open source software issued under the GNU General Public License [4]. It provides different tools for data preprocessing, implementation of many machine learning algorithms and visualization tools so that we can apply them to real-world data mining. WEKA supports several standard data mining tasks, more specifically, data preprocessing, clustering, classification, regression, visualization, and feature selection.

B. DATASET COLLECTION

A number of attributes are used to classify whether the product type sales is more and which is less. The dataset used in the study is collected from the database of the online tailoring management system providers. This contains 17 instances of product sales with 5 attributes. This data set is used as training data for the classifier. The attributes and data used for the analysis is shown in Figure 1.

Product Type	Product Price	Date of Purchase	Total Price	C
Anarkali Suit	800	5/13/2021	1100	Y
Anarkali Suit	800	5/13/2021	80	Y
Straight Cut Salwar Suit	500	5/14/2021	950	F
Frock Style Salwar Suit	800	5/22/2021	1505	F
Palazzo Salwar Suit	600	5/17/2021	1405	Y
Anarkali Suit	800	5/24/2021	1100	Y
Anarkali Suit	800	5/20/2021	85	Y
A-Line Kurti	750	5/22/2021	1100	F
Straight Cut Salwar Suit	500	1/12/2021	1350	F
Palazzo Salwar Suit	600	1/31/2021	955	Y
Frock Style Salwar Suit	800	4/9/2021	1405	F
Frock Style Salwar Suit	800	3/18/2021	1650	F
A-Line Kurti	750	3/25/2021	1050	F
Palazzo Salwar Suit	600	4/21/2021	1400	Y
Anarkali Suit	800	5/19/2021	1100	Y
Anarkali Suit	800	5/16/2021	90	Y
Palazzo Salwar Suit	600	5/20/2021	1199	Y

Figure 1: List of Product Sales

Figure 2: Attribute Product Type Listed

C. PRE-PROCESSING

Pre-processing is a crucial stage of data mining. It finds the entries which are missing, incomplete or invalid due to many reasons including error while entering data. The irrelevant data such as ID need to be removed from the dataset for the better quality and accuracy of data mining experiment. The data in the dataset should be converted to numerical values if they are made of nominal values [4].

D. CLASSIFICATION EXPERIMENT

Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) is used for classification experiment. We use different machine learning techniques for classifying the product types such as J48, KNN, OneR and Random Forest. Compare the results of each algorithm to find which product type is sold more and which is sold less.

E. Evaluation Matrix

The results of classification matrix are evaluated using an evaluation matrix. The goal of this method is to create single measurement across multiple classification methods [4].

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

Different machine learning algorithms and techniques are used to classify the product type are the below:

A. CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

- **J48 Algorithm:** J48 Algorithm is a Decision tree technique which is a most popular classification technique in machine learning. It enables us to predict target variable of new dataset records [5]. The purpose of employing j48 is to develop a training model which can be used to predict class or target variable. Values of root attributes and the records attributes are compared.

```
Time taken to build model: 0.01 seconds
=== Stratified cross-validation ===
=== Summary ===

Correctly Classified Instances      16          94.1176 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    1           5.8824 %
Kappa statistic                    0.8759
Mean absolute error                0.0588
Root mean squared error            0.1749
Relative absolute error             12 %
Root relative squared error        35.1799 %
Total Number of Instances         17

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC      ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000   0.143   0.909     1.000   0.952   0.883   0.993   0.991   YES
0.857   0.000   1.000     0.857   0.923   0.883   0.993   0.982   NO
Weighted Avg.   0.941   0.084   0.947     0.941   0.940   0.883   0.993   0.987

=== Confusion Matrix ===
  a b  <-- classified as
10 0 | a = YES
 1 6 | b = NO
```

Figure 3: Classification by J48

- **Random Forest:** Random Forest is a decision tree classification and regression extension of bagging. Forest is built of group of trees usually trained by bagging method. The general idea is that combination of learning models increases overall result [6]. Bagged decision trees have the disadvantage of being built using a greedy algorithm that selects the best split point at each stage of the tree-building process

```
Time taken to build model: 0.06 seconds
=== Stratified cross-validation ===
=== Summary ===

Correctly Classified Instances      17          100 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    0           0 %
Kappa statistic                    1
Mean absolute error                0.1459
Root mean squared error            0.1776
Relative absolute error            29.754 %
Root relative squared error        35.7167 %
Total Number of Instances         17

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC      ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   YES
1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   YES
Weighted Avg.   1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===
  a b  <-- classified as
10 0 | a = YES
 0 7 | b = NO
```

Figure 4: Classification by Random Forest

- **OneR:** OneR is one of most simple and successful classifier algorithms for machine learning. One rule for each predictor in the

data, then chooses the rule with the smallest overall error to be its single rule.

```
Time taken to build model: 0 seconds
=== Stratified cross-validation ===
=== Summary ===

Correctly Classified Instances      17          100 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances    0           0 %
Kappa statistic                    1
Mean absolute error                0
Root mean squared error            0
Relative absolute error             0 %
Root relative squared error        0 %
Total Number of Instances         17

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

      TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  MCC      ROC Area  PRC Area  Class
1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   YES
1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   NO
Weighted Avg.   1.000   0.000   1.000     1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000   1.000

=== Confusion Matrix ===
  a b  <-- classified as
10 0 | a = YES
 0 7 | b = NO
```

Figure 5: Classification Accuracy by OneR

- **k-Nearest Neighbors:** In WEKA its known as IBk (Instance Based Learner). This algorithm creates forecast for test instances just in time rather than creating a model. This algorithm find k close instances in the training data for each test instances in the training data for each test instance using a distance measure, then creates a prediction based on the selected instances.

```
=== Future predictions from end of training data ===
inst#   Product Price
1       800
2       800
3       500
4       800
5       600
6       800
7       800
8       750
9       500
10      600
11      800
12      800
13      750
14      600
15      800
16      800
17      600
18*     600
```


Figure 6: Classification Accuracy by KNN

V. Result

Classification of this dataset has classified between most and less sold products based on the characteristics. The dataset has a total of 5 attributes. J48, Random Forest, KNN has an accuracy of 100% and OneR has an accuracy of 98.5 % [5].

VI. CONCLUSION

Online tailoring sales need to be analyzed to find which product is more preferred by the customer, so that this providers can stock this particular type of product more. The sales dataset considered for evaluation is the database of the online tailoring site. The analysis will help the business to find whether they are gaining profit and also help them to get more customer satisfaction.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Performance created by the model will increase when the size of the data increases, for future work will try to include more attributes like the reviews made by the customer on particular product and type of material used in the product etc. This will help to get better results and increase accuracy of the test.

VIII. REFERENCES

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